

TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARD THEIR PROFESSION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN THEM AT THE SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL

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Abstract

The main concern of this research paper was to explore the relationship between teachers' attitudes toward their profession and students' academic achievement at public secondary schools utilizing a quantitative research approach. The population of the study consisted of 436 male teachers who were teaching in District Charsadda of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province. A sample of 210 teachers was selected through random cluster sampling technique as a sample for the study. The Teacher Attitude Index (TAI) Scale, developed by Schulte et al. (2005), was used for the collection of data. The average performance of the teachers in their subject area was calculated from the students' achievement scores in the Secondary School Annual Examination 2017 conducted by Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education Peshawar, KP. The data analysis showed that majority of the teachers had positive attitudes towards their profession. Further, it was revealed that teachers' attitude towards profession had a strong significant and positive relationship with students' academic achievement. It was recommended that government may take initiative to boost the teaching profession. In this regard the print media and social media should play the major role.

Keywords: Attitude, Profession, Academic Achievement, Secondary School Level

Introduction

Education is considered an important variable for the development of a nation. Education sector cannot be improved if the students' academic achievement are not improved. Academic achievement is the degree to which students achieve their learning goals and is typically assessed through exams (Conard, 2006). Educationists are trying to explore the factors that contribute to students' achievement. Atchia and Chinapah (2019) stated that a considerable 90.1% of students' achievement might be explained by socioeconomic factors, teacher, and school leadership variables.

Similarly, Ullah and Almani (2022) identified insufficient teachers, a learning environment, untrained teachers, weak school management, a Lack of teaching and reading materials, and inadequate classrooms in the school are important factors that influence students' performance. Academic achievement is complex scores that are influenced by a number of variables, such as personality traits and other personal factors (Batool, 2020).

Interestingly, although various factors have been identified in relation to students' achievement, research on internal factors like teachers' attitudes toward their profession was sparse in

the country. This provided a contextual gap, as the present population with different linguistic, and socio-cultural settings has remained previously under-researched and unexplored, which created the need for conducting the study. Vaughn (2012) stated that if teachers' dispositions, instruction and assessment are aimed at student achievement, then research is needed to determine whether any relationships exist between particular teacher dispositions and student achievement.

Attitude involves mental preparation relating to actions, postures, or beliefs, and determines what people see, hear, think and do. It is peoples' general tendency to respond to events, institutions, person, or group, and might be positive i.e. values, or negative i.e., prejudice (Barros & Elia, 2017). Shaheen (2014) described that attitude towards the profession, teaching experience, and interest in profession influence job commitment of teachers. Teachers' negative attitude towards teaching profession may affect students' performance negatively while teachers' positive attitude towards teaching profession would produce the right type of youth.

Thus it is important to have teachers with positive attitudes towards the profession. Teachers' attitude plays an important role in better achievement. The quality education depends on the attitude and behavior of teachers which influence their students directly or indirectly. It is argued that the role of teachers is that of a role model in education and students consider teachers as role models. Teachers need to improve performance by showing proper attitudes towards teaching profession.

1.2. Statement of the problem

The study aimed to determine the relationship between teachers' attitude towards profession and students' achievement at the secondary school level. Teachers, administrators, principals, educationists, and the community, in general, are concerned about improving the government school for adequate progress regarding student learning. The present government in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan has shown a profound concern about the quality of education and has stressed in the Education Sector Plan (2022) on hiring highly qualified teachers, providing Continuous Professional

Development, textbooks, examination reforms, and various in-service training programs.

Despite various efforts to improve the academic achievement of students studying at the secondary school level, only 59 % of the students passed the annual examination. The female passing rate was 64.7 % and the male students passing rate was 56.2 % which was a very low rate (BISE Peshawar result from Gazette, SSC Annual Examination 2022). A possible reason for this may be the attitudes, behaviors, and beliefs of teachers. Better academic accomplishment is largely influenced by teaching behaviors, which are influenced by attitudes.

According to Ulug, Ozde, and Eryilmaz (2011), the teacher plays a crucial role in education and is responsible for the majority of academic achievements. Teachers engaged in all those learning activities critical to the social, moral, and mental growth of their students. Teachers have to create a conducive school environment to facilitate the learning process for which a proper attitude is required.

1.3. Objective of the Research Study:

The objectives of the study were:

- a. To measure the attitude of teachers towards their students at the secondary school level.
- b. To determine the relationship between teachers' attitude toward their profession and students' academic achievement at the secondary school level.

1.4. Hypothesis of the Research Study

It was hypothesized that there was no relationship between teachers' attitudes toward their profession and academic achievement at the secondary school level.

2. Review of Literature

The review of relevant literature focusses on the attitudes that teachers have towards their profession and how those feelings relate to students' academic achievement. The literature on teacher's practices, expectations, beliefs, relationships and how these effects the students' achievement is important. Modern trends in education lay the responsibility of students 'intellectual and character development on schools and teachers. The abilities and characteristics of a good teacher also define a good education. Soric (2011) Stated that an

important task for schools is to identify and remediate factors influencing students' achievement. Ulug, Ozde and Eryilmaz, (2011) argued that teacher is an important part of education and can be considered as central to school outcome. It is argued that teachers' attitude towards their profession is important in determining school quality.

2.1. Concept of Attitude

Attitude is a tendency to classify events, objects, or behaviour and react to them with some consistency. Attitude is not directly observable and is inferred from the objective, evaluative responses of people (Renthlei & Malsawmi, 2015). According to Shah (2002) People have likes and dislikes, and possess certain degrees of favourability towards themselves, and their environment. Teacher training improves teachers' attitudes which affect students' achievement.

Maliki (2013) stated that attitudes influence behaviour and create a coherent value- system that impacts all aspects of social behaviour. In addition, Ahmadi (2015) argued that attitudes provide a framework for understanding the social environment and information processing through its various components. Attitudes are learned through life experiences and make people behave in characteristics towards issues, objects, persons, situation, or profession. Attitudes are personal and complex, are uniquely organized, and are a product of reactions to life experiences (Soibamcha & Pandey, 2016).

2.2. Teachers' Attitude

Teachers' beliefs influence the way they act, judge and perceive the classroom. Teachers' beliefs refer to the attitudes about teaching and students learning. Herrera (2010) found that teacher's attitudes can be explained by their subject matter knowledge, training, community involvement, self-awareness and approach to the school environment. Teacher's attitudes, beliefs and perceptions encourage or restrict teaching and learning in the classroom. Teaching influences students' cognition and thinking which mediates learning and achievement (Hornstra, Dennessen, Bakker, Bergh, & Voeten, 2010). There is a great need for awareness about how teachers' attitude toward their profession affects the education of learners.

2.3. Teachers' Attitude towards their Profession and Academic Achievement

Reddy (2017) stated that a profession implies acquisition of knowledge, skills and their application in the service. It is explained as an occupation based on intellectual study, training, and specialization. The teaching profession involves teacher's personal conduct and interaction with the school and community. An effective teaching profession is important for building up public intelligence and solving social problems. Teachers can build teaching profession by committing themselves to the profession through knowledge, devotion and sacrifice.

According to Shah (2009), academic achievement refers to the proficiency in academic work reflecting acquired knowledge in school subjects, and is represented by examination/test score. Similarly, Khamari and Guru (2013) also stated that achievement signifies accomplishment, gain, or performance of an individual on completion of a task. From an academic point of view, achievement means the level at which a student is functioning in different subjects measured through marks or scores.

Teachers' attitude towards teaching is important to determine teachers' feelings about teaching, beliefs, behaviour and learning environment. Teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession has a great impact on their performance. As Rao (2012) has insisted that teachers should have proper professional information based on sound philosophy, and should have positive attitude towards the teaching profession to enhance students' performance.

Additionally, Maliki (2013) also stated that attitude towards profession is an important factor for success in a profession. Teachers' attitude depends upon their characteristics and disposition which are highly interlinked. Teaching is dynamic profession requiring favourable attitude and competencies. Teachers' proficiency is related to their attitude toward teaching and positive attitudes of teachers helps in developing a conducive learning environment (Bhargava & Pathy, 2014).

The importance of the teaching profession has not decreased despite all the technological developments in the 21st century. According to Tok (2012, p.384) "People's attitudes towards

their profession have an effect on their performance". Attitude towards teaching has a great effect on academic achievement. It is an emotional, cognitive behavioural reaction to an action, situation, object, group, or individual. Varia (2016) investigated that teacher's beliefs, practices, and attitude are connected to strategies they use for coping with challenges they face in their professional lives. They form the learning environment and influence students achievement and motivation.

Shah (2009) concluded that teachers felt proud of their profession and made adjustments to the prevailing situation. Students were satisfied with the positive teacher behaviour. It was also reported that the relationship between the teachers' behaviour and students' achievement was positive.

Similarly, Folashade (2009) also reported a positive relationship between teachers' attitude and performance of students and found no significant relationship between the students' performance based on the gender of teachers. In contrast, Scrivner (2009) found no relationship between teachers' attitude towards profession and students' achievement in Mathematics. However, a positive relationship was found between teachers' attitude towards profession and reading achievement.

Mahmood (2011) found that teachers' professional attitude was positively related to job satisfaction and performance. It was reported that professional attitude combined with Job satisfaction was positively related with performance. In the same way, Soric (2011) reported a positive correlation between students' achievement and teachers' attitude while Owede and Yusuf (2014) found no correlation between teachers' disposition and students' performance but found a correlation between teachers'

reflective practice and students' performance. In a nutshell, various research studies offered mixed findings with regard to study's variables which provided need for further investigation.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

It was a descriptive correlational research study using the quantitative approach that aimed to determine the relationship between teachers' attitude and students' academic achievement at the secondary school level.

3.2. Population and Sample of the Study

The population of the study was consisted of teachers who were teaching at government secondary schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province. The population of District Charsadda in the Province was selected as an accessible population. In the Charsadda district, there were 76 secondary schools, in which 436 secondary school teachers were teaching. A sample of 210 teachers was selected for the study through a random cluster sampling technique.

3.3. Data Collection Instrument

Nine statements on Attitude toward Professionalism in The Teacher Attitude Index (TAI), developed by Schulte et al. (2005), were utilized for the collection of data. TAI is a valid and accurate scale for assessing teachers' attitudes (Scrivner, 2009), and utilizes a five-point Likert scale with responses ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Although, the instrument used for the study was valid and reliable but the researcher conducted pilot testing to determine its usability within the Pakistani context and of its Urdu version. The results indicated a good range for Cronbach Alpha.

Table 1. Reliability coefficients for Teachers' attitude towards profession

#	Dimensions of teachers' attitude	No of items	Mean	Alpha
	Teachers' attitude towards profession	9	4.3	0.84

The table 1. Shows that the Alpha value for the items/constructs on the scale was above 0.7 showing that the scale had internal consistency and was reliable.

The items in the scale were translated into Urdu to make them more understandable for the respondents and were presented along with its

original statements. The average score of the teachers in their subjects were calculated from the students' achievement scores in the Secondary School Annual Examination 2017 conducted by Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education Peshawar, KP.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

First of all, descriptive statistics were carried out for Teachers' Attitude toward Profession to answer the research question. Frequency, %age,

M, SD, and R were calculated. The data was then interpreted to give meaning to the analysis. The following table shows Teachers' attitude towards profession and was related to the research question of the study.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics on the items of Teachers' attitude towards profession (N=203)

#	Statements		SDA	DA	UNC	A	SA	M	SD	R
01	I view teaching as an important profession	f 3 % 1.5	0 0.0	1 .5	71 35.0	128 63.1	4.58	0.66	1	
02	I am punctual and reliable in my attendance	f 0 % 0	2 1.0	4 2.0	99 48.8	98 48.3	4.44	0.59	3	
03	I maintain a professional appearance	f 0 % 0	1 .5	1 .5	106 52.2	95 46.8	4.45	0.54	2	
04	I listen to colleagues ideas and suggestions to improve instruction	f 3 % 1.5	21 10.3	5 2.5	106 52.2	68 33.5	4.06	0.95	8	
05	I engage in discussions about new ideas in the teaching profession	f 4 % 2.0	18 8.9	5 2.5	117 57.6	59 29.1	4.03	0.92	9	
06	I communicate effectively with students, parents, and colleagues	f 2 % 1.0	16 7.9	14 6.9	107 52.7	64 31.5	4.06	0.89	7	
07	I uphold the laws and ethical codes governing the teaching profession	f 1 % .5	2 1.0	9 4.4	102 50.2	89 43.8	4.36	0.66	4	
08	I actively seek out professional growth opportunities	f 2 % 1.0	20 9.9	3 1.5	92 45.3	86 42.4	4.18	0.94	6	
09	I am committed to critical reflection for my professional growth	f 1 % .5	5 2.5	6 3.0	103 50.7	88 43.3	4.34	0.70	5	

In the light of the above analysis in of table 2, it can be interpreted that majority of teachers (98.1%) viewed teaching as an important profession (R=1, SD=0.66, M=4.58) and 90.0% maintained a professional appearance (R=2, SD=0.54, M=4.45). Majority of teachers (97.1%) claimed that they were punctual and reliable in attendance (R=3, SD=0.59, M=4.44), and 94% teachers upheld the laws and ethical codes governing the teaching profession (R=4, SD=0.66, M=4.36). Most of them (94%) were of the opinion that they were committed to critical reflection on their professional growth (R=5, SD=0.70, M=4.34) and 87.7% sought out professional growth opportunities (R=6, SD=0.94, M=4.18). Majority of teachers (84.2%) claimed that they could communicate effectively with students, parents, and colleagues (R=7,

SD=0.89, M=4.06). 85.7% teachers listened to their ideas and suggestions to improve instruction (R=8, SD=0.95, M=4.06), while 86.7% respondents engaged in a discussion about new ideas in the profession (R=9, SD=0.92, M=4.03).

The above analysis shows that teachers, in general, viewed teaching to be an important profession and claimed to maintain a professional appearance. They also claimed to be reliable in attendance and upheld the ethical codes related to teaching. They claimed to have critical reflection about teaching and sought out opportunities for professional growth. They could successfully communicate with each other, parents, and students and listened to ideas for improving instruction.

Table 3. One sample t-test for teachers' attitude towards profession (N=203)

One-Sample Test							95% Interval Difference	Confidence of the Upper
Test Value = 3								
	M	SD	t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper
Teachers' attitude towards profession	4.28	0.49	36.980	202	.000	1.279	1.21	1.35

P<0.05

The data in the table 3 shows that the mean value of teachers' attitude towards profession was 4.28 which was significantly higher than the test value 3. The t-value is 36.98 which is significant at

p<0.05 level. It also shows that the mean difference is 1.28 higher than the test value. It shows that majority of respondents were on the agreement side.

4.2. Test of hypothesis

Table 4. Pearson correlation between teachers' attitude towards the profession and student achievement (N=203)

Variables		Pearson coefficient (r) with student achievement	
		r	sig
1	Teachers' attitude towards profession	0.511	.000
2	Student average score		

P<0.05

The table 4 shows that the value of r with student achievement score was 0.511 which was statistically positively significant at p<0.05 level. The researcher, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis and accepted that there was a positive and statistically significant relationship between teachers' attitude towards profession and students' achievement.

towards teaching profession. In contrast, Soibamcha and Pandey (2016) indicated those teachers' unfavourable attitudes towards teaching profession, however; more qualified teachers seemed to be having more positive attitudes toward teaching profession than the less qualified teachers. It is argued that teachers should possess some professional and personal characteristics and attitudes. Chen and Chang (2006) stated that a professional attitude is the commitment of teacher to his profession. Teaching is a versatile profession in which elements of attitude, practice, and skill interacting together.

4.3. Discussion

Attitudes towards teaching are an important factor for success in teaching. Success in the teaching profession requires dedication and patience; and is a continuous process. To become a successful teacher, it is important to like the profession and willingly do the work. The study found that teacher had positive attitude towards their profession. The finding is in line with Kumar (2015) who revealed a significant positive relation between the attitudes of senior secondary school teachers towards teaching. Similarly, Sarkar and Behera (2016) reported that the attitude of college teachers in West Bengal was neither favourable nor unfavourable towards teaching profession meaning that teachers displayed an average or satisfactory attitude

Although it was hypothesized that there would be no relationship between teachers' attitude toward their profession and students' academic achievement. But the study found a strong positive link between the two. This is in line with Folashade (2009) and Mahmood (2011) who reported a positive relationship between teachers' attitude and performance of students and found no significant relationship between the students' performance based on the gender of teachers, but is in contrast with Scrivner (2009) and Ries (2015) who found no relationship between teachers' attitude towards profession and

students' achievement. Similar to findings, Soric (2011) and Ahmadi (2015) reported a positive correlation between students' achievement and teachers' attitude while Owede and Yusuf (2014) found no correlation between teachers' disposition and students' performance.

In conclusion, teachers' negative and positive attitudes towards profession affect students' achievement. Therefore, attention should be paid to the in-service and pre-service training and the process should begin by professional recognition of teachers. Teachers should reflect about and identify the aspects of teaching that require change. Teachers should understand their problems to reach solutions (Barros and Elia, 2017). Teachers' attitudes are context outcomes rooted in experience, which are developed through interactions and are established with time. Attitudes can be changed by individuals through awareness of new methods to deal with their environment. Professional and educational change is related and it is possible to modify teaching attitudes by teaching programs.

4.4. Limitations of the Study

The study used a self-reported survey, the results may not accurately reflect the true picture of teachers' responses to the statements of the instrument. Mental habits are not restricted to the questions on the surveys and are not always caught by a predetermined list of statements of the instruments utilized in the research (Vaughn, 2012). Further the study was limited to a small sample size that may introduce bias into the results. Moreover, the study was restricted to higher secondary and government schools in the Charsadda district. It is probable that private schools and schools in other districts have distinct school climates, which could have an impact on how teachers acquire their dispositions.

4.5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study concluded that majority of the teachers had positive attitude towards teaching profession. Further, the study revealed a positive and statistically significant relationships between teachers' attitudes toward their profession and academic achievement. Teachers' attitudes toward their profession were a good indicator of their academic achievement. Therefore, it was

recommended that government may take initiative to boost the teaching profession. In this regard the print media and social media should play the major role.

4.6. Directions for Future Research:

To further support the findings, observational and interviewing methods might be used in subsequent research. In order to increase the validity and make it a useful tool for possible policy changes, future research may also be carried out with a larger sample size and a broader coverage involving both public and private schools in urban and rural settings.

References

- Ahmadi, M. (2015). The factors affecting attitudes and academic achievement in art course in secondary school students in Zanzibar from the perspective of teachers. *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Sciences*, 2 (3), 171-174. https://www.ijires.org/administrator/components/com_jresearch/files/publications/IJIREs_287_Final.pdf
- Archia, S. M. C., & Chinapah. V. (2019). Factors affecting academic achievement of secondary school students in Mauritius. *Journal of Education and Research*, 9(1), 70-90. doi.org/10.3126/jer.v9i1.28825
- Barros, S. D. S., Elia, M. F. (2017). *Physics teachers' attitudes: How do they affect the reality of the classroom and models for change?* <https://www.univie.ac.at/pluslucis/Archiv/ICPE/D2.html>
- Batool, S.S. (2020) Academic achievement: Interplay of positive parenting, self-esteem, and academic procrastination, *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 72(2), 174-187. doi: 10.1111/ajpy.12280
- Bhargava, A., & Pathy, M. K. (2014). Attitude of student teachers towards teaching profession. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE*, 15(3), 27-36. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1043694.pdf>
- Chen, J., & Chang, C. (2006). Testing the whole teacher approach to professional development: A study of enhancing early childhood teachers' technology proficiency. *Early Childhood Research and*

- Practice, 5(1), 1-18. Retrieved October 15, 2017 from the Early Childhood Research and Practice Website: <http://ecrp.uiuc.edu/v8nl/chen.html>
- Conard, M. A. (2006). Aptitude is not enough: How personality and behavior predict academic performance. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 40(3), 339-346. doi:10.1016/j.jrp.2004.10.003
- Folashade, A. (2009). Teachers' attitude and gender factor as determinant of pupils' performance in primary science. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal*, 3(1), 326-332. Retrieved January 2, 2018 from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/afrev/article/viewFile/43578/27103>
- Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (2020). Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Education Sector Plan (KPESP) 2020-25. <https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/sites/default/files/ressources/pakistan-khyber-pakhtunkhwa-esp.pdf>
- Herrera, J. C. (2010). *Teacher beliefs and practices: their effects on students' achievement in the urban school setting*. Ph.D. Dissertation, College of Education, Kansas State University. <http://krex.k-state.edu/dspace/handle/2097/3889>
- Khamari, J., & Guru, N. (2013). Relationship of attitude and achievement of secondary school students. *OSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)* e-ISSN: 2320-7388, 1(3), 50-54. <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jrme/papers/Vol-1%20Issue-3/H0135054.pdf?id=1677>
- Khamari, J., & Guru, N. (2013). Relationship of attitude and achievement of secondary school students. *OSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)* e-ISSN: 2320-7388, 1(3), 50-54. <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jrme/papers/Vol-1%20Issue-3/H0135054.pdf?id=1677>
- Kumar, A. (2015). Attitude towards teaching profession in relation to adjustment among senior secondary school teachers. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 4(4), 830-833. <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v4i4/SUB153131.pdf>
- Mahmood, N. (2011). *A comparative study of contractual and regular teachers' professional attitude towards job satisfaction and job performance*. Ph.D. dissertation, Division of Education, University of Education, Lahore
- Maliki, A. E. (2013). The attitude of teachers in Yenagoa Local Government area Bayelsa state Nigeria, towards the teaching profession: Counselling Implications. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 2(2), 61-67. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/4635/455ab76fcfdb558b4602df5eb7163893df4c.pdf>
- Owede, V.C., & Yusuf, A. (2014). *Teachers' disposition and reflective practice as correlates of students' performance in social studies in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State*. PanAfrican university institute. https://www.musero.org.ng/publications/teachers_disposition_and_reflective_practice_correlates_students_performance_social_studies_yenagoa_metropolis_bayelsa_state.pdf
- Rao, K. S. (2012). Study of the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards teaching profession. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and Social Sciences (IJREISS)*, 2 (6), 13-23. www.indusedu.org
- Reddy, Y. M. (2017). An Influence of certain psycho-sociological factors on teacher effectiveness of primary school teachers. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*. 6 (1), 246-264. www.ijsr.net
- Renthlei, M. L. & Malsawmi, H. (2015). Construction of an attitude scale towards teaching profession: A study among secondary school teachers in Mizoram. *International Journal of Arts, Humanities, and Management Studies*, 1(4), 29-36. <https://www.academia.edu/12392121/>
- Ries, J. A. (2015). *Teacher disposition related to student achievement. Does it matter?* Ph.D. dissertation, Cardinal Stritch University. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/c965d00e047dbb354bf8e069a206be58/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>

- Sarkar, D., & Behera, S.K. (2016). Attitude of college teachers towards teaching profession. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4(11), 834-839. doi:10.12691/education-4-11-9
- Schulte, L., Edick, N., Edwards, S., & Mackiel, D. (2005). *The development and validation of the teacher dispositions index*. www.usca.edu/essays/vol122004/schulte.pdf
- Scrivner, C. M. (2009). *The relationship between student achievement and teacher attitude: A correlational study*. Ph.D. Dissertation, North Central University Graduate Faculty of the School of Education. <https://pqdtopen.proquest.com/doc/305175883.html?FMT=AI>
- Shah, M. (2002). *Comparative effectiveness of teacher training in enhancing the professional attitudes of B.Ed. students admitted in institutes of education and research NWFP*. College of Education Islamabad and Allama Iqbal Open University Islamabad. PhD Dissertation, Allama Iqbal Open University Islamabad <http://pr.hec.gov.pk/Chapters/77-0.pdf>
- Shah, S. S. A. (2009). Impact of teacher's behaviour on the academic achievement of university students. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning*, 6(1), 69-74. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ884620>
- Shaheen, S. S. (2014). Eligibility versus entrance test. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(10), 168-171 <http://www.ajms.co.in/sites/ajms2015/index.php/ajms/article/view/673/551>
- Soibamcha, E., & Pandey, N. (2016). The attitude of teachers towards the teaching profession. *Global journal of interdisciplinary social sciences*, 5(3), 49-51.
- Soric, T. M.(2011). *The impact of teacher attitudes on academic achievement in disadvantaged schools*. Master of Education thesis, The University of Toledo. <http://utdr.utoledo.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1748&context=theses-dissertations>
- Tok, T. N. (2012). *Teacher candidates' attitudes towards the teaching profession in Turkey*. Alberta Journal of Educational Research, 58(3), 381-403. <http://ajer.journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/ajer/article/view/1055>
- Ullah, N., & Almani, A. S. (2022). Factors affecting students' academic performance: A case study of secondary schools of Makran Division Balochistan, Pakistan. *Webology*, 19, 2749-2764. <http://www.webology.org>
- Ulug, M., Ozde, M. S., & Eryilmaz, A. (2011). The effects of teachers' attitudes on students' personality and performance. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences* 30, 738-742. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.144
- Varia, V. (2016). A Study of professionalism of secondary school teachers with respect to education board. *IJRDO Journal Of Educational Research* , 2(7), 76-103.
- Vaughn, K. A. (2012). *Teacher Dispositions and Student Achievement*. Ph.D. dissertation, Claremont Graduate University <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED549802>
- Vaughn, K. A. (2012). *Teacher dispositions and student achievement*. PhD Dissertation, Claremont Graduate University. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED549802>